

E-MARKETING: STRATEGY OF INCREASED PRODUCTION TO THE COOPERATIVE ROLE OF MICRO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES)

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Abstract

The cooperative is a pillar of the economy of Indonesia, its existence is guaranteed by law. Production cooperatives in Indonesia were acting as a place to accommodate the goods produced or manufactured by the members, realizing the maximum income by way of fostering and developing the potential of each. SMEC is one form of the usual effort is supported by a cooperative of their funding. SMEC has problems in marketing their products especially in the era of information such as current. The purpose of this Writing is to overcome the problem facing the SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in terms of marketing products as well as helping provide education regarding the development of a more professional through the website E-Marketing.com. Marketing through E-Marketing will be managed by a cooperative of production to be able to accommodate any businessmen who are members. These writings are the library research presented in descriptive and supported by some of the literature relevant to the problems examined. The application of E-Marketing for SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES can be the solution to production cooperatives in Indonesia to grow, SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES development in Indonesia is able to compete in national and global markets.

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1. Introduction

The cooperative is a pillar of the economy of Indonesia, then the existence and its existence is guaranteed by law. Production cooperatives in Indonesia served as a refuge or a container to hold the goods produced or manufactured by a Member, have functions to develop the potential and ability of Member economies in improving economic and social well-being, realizing people's income in a fair and equitable manner unite, foster and develop any potential there is. Micro, small and medium enterprises (UMKM) have an important role in the economy in Indonesia. SMEC has the proportion of 99.99% of total trade in Indonesia or as much as 56.54 million units [1]. In the year 2018 sectors of micro, small, and medium enterprises have a great contribution towards the gross domestic product increased from 60.34 percent to 57.84 percent in the last five years. Labor absorption in this sector also increased, from 96.99 percent to 97.22 percent over the same period. [2]

Studies conducted by Bank Indonesia (2015) shows that SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in Indonesia and implementation of the policy face some problems. The first problem arises because the definition differs between different government agencies. The second problem facing the SMEC is the question of the structural establishment and operation of business entities. The

third problem, SMEC trouble getting information and access to many things operationally. For example, the difficulty in marketing, no belief in an institution because of the absence of forms of legal entities, has no financial statements, does not have collateral, the inability to make comprehensive credit proposal. Whereas at the time of the current technology is very sophisticated but small and medium businessmen still had some problems in the development of product marketing.

is electronic commerce which can be utilized by perpetrators of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to be able to market its goods with wider. According to Mendag (2018) that 90% of goods marketed on e-commerce in Indonesia mostly imported goods is [3]. According to Mendag that 90% of the stuff on sale at e-commerce in Indonesia mostly imported good is [3]. This is unfortunate in which SMEC is supposed to develop will be replaced by the imported good. When imported goods sold at online then the SMEC will compete against such products. Solutions for development in marketing Products SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in Indonesia can be done through innovation the role of cooperative production with optimized e-commerce technology in the development of product marketing. The perpetrators of the SMEC will team up with production cooperatives as a member so that they can trade off products small medium through the application of E-marketing, where is E-marketing only sells original products SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to be able to promote the development and marketing of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.

1.1. Problem Identification

1. What is the contribution of small medium enterprises and cooperatives against Indonesia's economic growth and the problems encountered by small and medium trade and cooperatives in Indonesia? What is the mechanism of the website E-marketing as a product marketing for small and medium trade?
2. What is the mechanism of the website E-marketing as a marketing product for SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES trade?
3. How does E-Commerce urgency against E-marketing as a means of marketing products SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES?

2. Theoretical Review

2.1. Production cooperative

The cooperative is one of the economic institutions, in addition to business entities and Government-private business entities. In the economy of a country, each business entity has a separate function and contribution. The cooperative has two different sides but in line IE in line, namely Assembly and company. However, often seen as a bevy of cooperative social institutions are understood. Conversely, as the company understood is a business entity controlled by capital for profit. There are several types of cooperatives in Indonesia, a cooperative based on the status of members, the cooperative based on the highest level, cooperatives based on function and by type of cooperatives. Cooperative production included in the cooperative based on the type of business members. Production cooperative is a cooperative that has the purpose to help members or doing business together. Production cooperative will act as a container to allocate business results, as well as its members, provide assistance regarding market results as members of agricultural cooperatives, the results of the creative industries and others.

2.2. SMEC

SMEC is a form of productive economic efforts being undertaken by the individual or business entity of individuals who meet the criteria of micro, small and medium enterprises.

In the perspective of business, SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES classified into four groups, namely:

- 1.The informal sector, such as SMEC traders times five.
- 2.Micro SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES is the SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES with the capabilities of the nature of craftsmen but lacks the soul to develop entrepreneurial efforts.
- 3.Dynamic small business is a group of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES capable of entrepreneurship with the partnership (receiving job subcontract) and export.
- 4.Fast Moving Enterprise is a SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES who have an accomplished entrepreneur and has been ready to transform into a huge undertaking.

The existence of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in Indonesia can say strong because it is spread across the country and mastered about 99% Indonesia business activities, with more than 98% of the apparent status of microenterprises. It also results in SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES have a great contribution to the economy Indonesia, as reported by one of the page Detik.com on July 10, 2018, and then stating that SMEC was able to boost economic growth. The statement reinforced with DPP Syriac HIPPI Motik i.e. productive sector of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES can provide more jobs from 107.6 million inhabitants of Indonesia and contribute to 60.0% of GDP against Indonesia. The existence of such SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES should be encouraged and developed with the full support of the Government. With the support and development of small and medium businesses, are expected to contribute to the greater economic welfare of society reached Indonesia.

2.3. Marketing

Marketing is one of a very important stage in the business and corporate world. Competitive marketing among business industries in Indonesia currently is getting sharper, it is influenced by the development of technology in the modern era as it currently. In Indonesia, there are two types of marketing namely marketing online and offline marketing. According to Kotler's online channel is a channel that can be reached by someone through a computer and a modem, which connects a computer with modem telephone network thus causing computers can access and reach out to a wide array of information services Online [4]. While according to Kienan stating that online marketing is conducting business online which forms the most obvious is to sell products to consumers online. In simple it is to create, manage and expand the commercial relationship online [5]. In Indonesia, there are also offline marketing or often referred to as marketing director. Based on the direct marketing association (DMA), Direct marketing (direct marketing) is a system of interactive marketing that uses one or more advertising media to generate the response and/or transaction that can be resized at a place [6]. According to Kotler itself, there is a channel that is used in direct marketing such as face-to-face, direct mail marketing, through catalogs, kiosks, and other direct-response media

2.4. E-Commerce

The growth of online shopping in Indonesia fairly rapidly, and the lack of crime over the internet has also contributed to belief and comfort the higher against online shopping survey conducted by market /research firm Ipsos (independent run by professional researchers, established in France now has offices in 84 countries) in 2012 showed that 69% of Internet users in Indonesia do a web search to find the products they want to buy, and of the total number of respondents as much as the 48% made a purchase online items [7].

E-commerce is electronic commerce which can be utilized by small and medium businessmen or business star for production of goods can market more broadly. It is unfortunate that according to Mendag 90% of goods traded in dollars e-commerce in Indonesia are generally imported goods. This is unfortunate in which SMEC is supposed to develop will be replaced by imported goods.

3. Research Method

Engineering data collection paper descriptive research method. Descriptive analysis, research namely research that seeks to explain or describe the events that occur on objects of research in the later explained, analyzed, and presented in such a way, so that it becomes a systematic overview [8]. The data used in this research is the primary data and secondary data. Primary data obtained from through three ways i.e., observation, community interviews and Triangulation (checking of the truth). While secondary data obtained from printed books, official website, journals and articles that have been identified, analyzed, explained and interpreted, so it becomes a job that can be accounted for.

4. Result and Discussion

5.1 Potency and Contribution of Cooperatives and SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES towards the growth of the Indonesian economy and knowing the problems faced by perpetrators of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES and cooperatives in Indonesia.

Micro, small and medium enterprises (UMKM) is a sector which has a major role for the economy of Indonesia. Characteristics of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES according to the World Bank in the LPMI and Bank Indonesia (2015).The number of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES is estimated at 60.7 million units and most are micro-scale businesses (98,73 percent). The biggest growth is present in the secondary businesses namely amounting to 8.7 percent. In the same period, the capacity of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to absorb the labor continuously experiencing a trend that is amounting to 5.9 percent. In 2015, the number of labor SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES reached over 132.3 million. But most of the SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES labor(88.6 percent) is still an informal labor on a micro-scale enterprise [9].

SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES contribute to growth in Indonesia among others, as a contributor to GDP, absorbing labor, and containers to create new businesses as well as the high export value accounted for the economy of Indonesia. From the side of the SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES absorbing labor as well as a container for creating SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES business. From the huge contribution of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to the economy, it has a big obstacle to be able to develop in the current era of globalization. The constraints often faced by SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in developing their activities such as difficulties in the capital, difficulties in developing products and marketing of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES products. Many SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES produce good quality products but cannot market their products and lack of government attention to the development of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.

As one of the perpetrators of the national economy, the cooperative has a mission as economic stabilizers in addition as an agent of development. The economic crisis that hit the national economy has demonstrated to many that the management of the economy that relies on big companies have made a fragile base of the national economy. When the financial crisis occurred, many large companies are experiencing stagnation and derailed his efforts. But amid the weak condition of the national economy turns out small businesses, medium businesses and cooperatives can still survive and become a beachhead for a role in administering the national economy.

Cooperative is one of the economic institutions, in addition to business entities and Government-private business entities. The cooperative has a very important role in the development of the economy in Indonesia, namely one to strengthen the economy of the people as the basic strength and the resilience of the economy. There are several types of cooperatives in Indonesia, a cooperative based on the status of the members, based on grades, a cooperative based on its function and its business by type of cooperatives. Cooperative production included

in the cooperative based on the type of business members. Production cooperative is a cooperative that has the purpose to help members or doing business together. Production cooperative will act as a container to allocate business results of its members as well as provide assistance regarding marketing deliverables such as the agricultural cooperative members, the results of the creative industries and others.

5.2 The mechanism of application E-marketing as a marketing product for SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES trade?

Based on the conditions of existence of cooperatives and SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES that have a huge contribution towards economic growth. It takes something that could help significantly in the unifying role among the agencies of cooperation with SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to be able to collaborate and optimize the existing activities. Needed a bridge to SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to cooperate against the Cooperative, that is using E-marketing website. E-Marketing is a website that has the function as a means of marketing the results of local SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES through digital technology. E-marketing in addition to developing products SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES had a role to reduce the number of existing unemployment. Where the courier that will send the item is a member of the cooperative. following the empowerment Schemes conducted by the cooperative against the SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.

Gambar 5.1. The scheme of cooperation between Cooperatives with SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in product marketing

Source: Author's Analysis.

From the picture above, the application of the scheme of cooperation between cooperatives with SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in marketing products can be described as follows:

1. Each of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES will register to be a member of the cooperative production to perform marketing activities using website E-Marketing.
2. The production cooperative has an e-marketing website where the website will help market local MSME products so that they can be better known by the wider community. As well as reducing the level of unemployment that exists because the courier who will deliver the goods to the buyer is a member of the cooperative as well. The advantage of this scheme is that every SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES can join with the requirements of being registered as a member of a production cooperative.

4.1. E-Commerce Urgency towards E-marketing As a means of marketing SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES products.

The cooperative must have a forum that can accommodate all the problems of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES and their members and also improve the Indonesian economy. Production cooperatives have an important role in the development of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES members. The role of production cooperatives helps develop SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES from management to marketing. Therefore the cooperative has an initial step in helping SMALL

MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to market their products, namely using the E-Marketing website created by cooperative cooperatives that focus on the products of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES or creative industries in Indonesia. The E-Marketing website creates a forum for SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to be able to market their products or processed products to every SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES that has become a member. But E-Marketing is not only focused on online sales but also on employment for people who are looking for work. The positive value of E-Marketing is that the courier who will deliver the goods to the buyer is a member of the cooperative. So that not only SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES industry members get the benefit but there are cooperative members who also get the benefit from where he works as a courier. In the business world strategy in terms of marketing is very important, where this is what will later determine the success or failure of a business. In this activity of empowering SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES, the urgency of marketing must be considered as knowing what products consumers want and evaluating products that will be produced through innovation to achieve their goals. SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES and cooperatives experience difficulties in developing due to inappropriate marketing practices.

Technological progress should be able to have a positive impact on SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES because they can help in product marketing. However, only a few percents of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES have taken advantage of this, this is due to the ignorance of other SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES players who have not used technology facilities because there is still a businessman who has not been able to and can operate technology or online facilities. Related to these issues, it is necessary to have intensive empowerment and training of these business actors in order to be able to compete with other business institutions in marketing.

The role of technology in helping the empowerment and marketing of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES is very important where technology will always experience renewal. If SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES are lagging behind in the development of technology, it will also have a large negative impact, as it will experience difficulties in development and will be less competitive with other business institutions. To help with the development and empowerment of this technology the information technology is online and offline.

Online technology can be a place for SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to develop their businesses, one of them is E-MARKETING.com. E-MARKETING.com is one website that is intended to help SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in marketing their products, where one of the problems experienced by SMEs, in general, is marketing. The SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES work system is the same as most online shops in general, but what makes the difference between E-MARKETING.com itself provides marketing tools and provides insight into SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES players regarding innovative products that can be references to develop their business.

5. Conclusion

The basic principle of E-marketing web aims to develop the local potential of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to be able to compete with imported products using technology in the 4.0 era. The process of optimizing product marketing through cooperatives with the E-Marketing website is by way of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES registering themselves as members of cooperatives and registering products to be sold by filling in the existing forms. Buyers of SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES products on the E-Marketing website are not only members of cooperatives but the wider community who are not members of cooperatives can buy through the E-marketing website. Besides being focused on marketing cooperatives also provide work for members of cooperatives as couriers in distributing or distributing products purchased by customers. So that it can reduce the number of unemployed in Indonesia.

6. Recommendation

In writing this scientific paper it would be better if there was a discord and suggestions for the development of E-Marketing in the future so as to be able to support cooperatives and SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES to contribute optimally to the Indonesian economy. The government of the relevant ministries and cooperatives needs to make policies related to synergies between financial institutions related to protection and law enforcement as examples of control of business competition in the industrial sphere. Academics play a role in developing program innovations through research conducted to help SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISES in developing businesses

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Appendix

